

A Study on Prospects and Challenges of Self-help Groups in Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

Self-employment is a significant step to have sustained incomes and remove the shackles of poverty. Self help groups are voluntary gatherings of persons who share needs or problems that are not being addressed by Existing organizations, institutions, or other types of groups Rapid progress in SHG formation has now turned into an empowerment movement among women across the country. Economic empowerment results in women's ability to influence or make decision, increased self confidence, better status and role in household etc. The participation of women in SHGs made a significant impact on their empowerment both in social and economic aspects. The main objective of this study is to find the impact of microfinance in pushing back rural poverty. Hence, the socio-economic status of the respondents both in pre- and post-SHG situations, were sought to be analyzed. The present study addresses issues related to the performance of self-help groups. Various research gaps have been identified that need to be studied immediately to strengthen the performance of self-help groups is found that the income of members of Self Help Group has increased after joining.

Keywords: SHG, microfinance, empowerment, performance.

Introduction

Self help groups are increasing rapidly in our country. Especially in rural India it works very well and shows good effect on the economy and society. With the help of SHG's lot of poor women become self employed with the available local resources and their skills and knowledge they started their own business. Now a day's SHGs play pivotal role in the rural economy. SHG signifies not only empowering women but also in respect of investment, production and marketing effort of women. This is one of the most effective ways to promote the micro-finance in the society & seen as an important tool for the empowering of women. Self Help Group (SHG) is a small voluntary association of poor people, preferably from the same socioeconomic background. They come together for the purpose of solving their common problems through selfhelp and mutual help. The SHG promotes small savings among its members. The savings are kept with a bank. This common fund is in the name of the SHG. Usually, the number of members in one SHG does not exceed twenty.

Statement of the Problem

The concept of Self-help group has brought revolutionary changes in rural economy today paving the way for self reliance to the rural people specially to the weaker section it has provide to be the remedy for many problems of the rural folks such as poverty unemployment under employment exploitations social neglecting and operation poor infrastructural facility and standard of living and so on. The impact of SHG have many dimensions, viz. social economic political and personal. It is time relevant to study on this as its growth within a short period is multifold in Tamilnadu. The same trend is recorded in Thoothukudi District.

Objectives

- To study the Growth of Self-Help Group
- To Study the various schemes available to Self-Help group through private and government agencies.
- To study the utility of borrowings by Self-Help Group.

Need for the Study

In this study, an attempt ha been made to know about prospects and challenges of self-help group at Thoothukudi District. This study provides information on the performance of self-help groups. The study on prospects of self-help group reached the people.

Methodology of the Study

The present study is an empirical research based on secondary data. Relevant secondary was collected from books, Projects, Journals, periodical and annual reports.

Limitation of the Study

Since the study is based on secondary data, the researcher had to depend on the information given from the Journals, Projects.

Review of Literature

Jayaraman (2015) in his article entitled performance analysis of fisher women self help groups, states that contrary to the common belief that poor women are not credit worthy, they are far more credit worthy, honest and most importantly 'bankable'. His study showed that the SHGs did play a positive role in helping the fisher folk in their socio economic development, emancipation and empowerment. The SHG has enabled them to live with self esteem and gain the awareness that everyone has a right to live so.

Manju Panwar (2016) in the article on role of SHGs is strengthen in grassroots democracy-experiences of Haryana, revealed that, the intervention of SHG members and the gram Sabah meetings are held a per the provisions of Haryana panchayat raj act,1944. It leads to increase in attendance of Gram Sabah meeting and persuaded their own family member to attend the Gram Sabah meeting. By the interventions of SHG, the Gram Sabah meeting agenda has changed according the needs of the society like social evils and the problems of increased alcoholism and other retrograde trends in rural society such as female feticide.

Vijayachandran pillai and Harikumar (2017) in their article self help groups in kerala, have focused on various innovative programmes and schemes to address the issue of poverty and unemployment prevailing in India they pointed out that SHGs faced problems in different areas such as inadequate training facilities, problems of marketing, lack of stability and unity especially among women SHGs, weak financial management and inadequate support from online departments.

Further, they have suggested that, in marketing of SHGs product, the state level organization Kerams (Kerala Rural Development and Marketing Society) should extend their activities throughout the state. NGOs and financial institutions can play a significant role in empowering women. School without any discrimination. It will definitely lead to their empowerment.

Theoretical Perspective

Introduction

The term self-help group of SHG can be used to describe wide range of financial and non-financial association. However in India it has to come refer to a form of Accumulating Saving Credit association (ASC). Self-help groups which are also called as mutual help or mutual aid groups or thrift and credit groups, composed of peers who share a similar mental, emotional, or physical problem, or who are interested in a focus issue, such as educational or parenting.

In other words the members join together with the intention findings a solution to a common problem such as medical issues, livelihood generation or watershed management, with a degree for self-sufficiency. Historically, people banded together to improve their chances for survival by pooling their social and economic resources; however, contemporary groups are more likely to organize around them or problems.

Meaning of Self-Help Group

As far as our country is concerned one has to follow the norm developed by the NABARD for understanding the concept of self-help group. According to NABARD, a SHG is a group of about 20 people from a homogeneous class, who come together for addressing their common problems. These groups normally posses people who are economically and socially weaker. These enroll members from all walks of life but between the age group of 18 years to 60 years.

Definition

According to G.P.Singh SHG is a collection of people who have common people that cannot be solve individually and have therefore decided to form into groups and take joint action to solve the problems.

Characteristics of Self-help Groups

Based on local conditions and requirements, the self-help groups have evolved their own characteristics, however, some of the common characteristics of functioning of these groups are indicated below;

- The groups usually create a common fund by contributing their small savings on a regular basis.
- Most of the groups themselves, or with help of ngos evolve flexible system of workings and managing their pooled resources in a democratic way, with participation of every member in decision-making.
- Request for loans are considered by the group in their periodic meeting and competing claims on limited resources are settled by consensus.
- Loan is offered mainly on trust with a bare minimum documentation and without any security.
- The amount of loans are small, frequent and for short duration.
- The loans cover a variety of purpose, some of which are non-traditional and rather un-conventional.

Findings

The data analysis in the context of the above objectives reveals the followings

- Most of the members of the SHG belongs to the age group of 20-40 especially to age group of above 50 all the members are female and most of the members are married. Thus most of the areas are members of the SHG in the study area are middle aged married women.

- Most of the members of the SHG belong to back ward class, scheduled caste, and most back ward community people are in the SHG as members.
- Most of the members of the SHG in the study area have only primary and secondary level of education.
- Most of the members are either unemployed or employed in unorganized sector. People employed on organized sector and salaried jobs are very negligible in numbers.
- Most of the members of SHG in the study area are in nuclear family setups.
- Most of the members of SHG in the study area have good amount of experience as number and the duration of membership ranges between 3 years to 7 years.
- Most of the members in the study area have got information about the SHG through relatives and friends.
- Most of the SHG members monthly contribution is Rs.50. This monthly contribution will be deposited in the bank.
- Availing loan for household needs and move with others are the two important motives behind joining SHG members in the study area.
- Development of saving habit and gaining knowledge about banking of the members are the important impacts of the SHG on their members.
- All the members of SHG in the study area are borrowing loan from banks.
- Most of the members of SHG in the study area are waiting to avail loan for a period of less than one month.
- Most of the members of SHG in the study area are paying interest rate of Rs.1.5.
- Availing loan for agriculture and buy cattle are the purpose of getting loan.
- The study that all SHG members are facing the problem of lack of training. Government should conduct the training programme.
- Most of the members have positive opinion about the performance SHG and almost all are satisfied with their membership in SHG. Most of the SHG members are found to confident persons.
- Most of the members of SHG in the study area are repaying the loan on monthly basis.
- All the members of SHG on the study area have got micro level benefit.

Conclusion

The SHG are playing vital role in economic development of rural people. This study deals with the some important prospects and challenges. SHG try to develop skill of entrepreneurship among members, so that their earning capacity improves. Though they seem to be profitable they are confined to rural area. They suffer from certain problems which are rectifiable the remedy lies in giving training in the areas of marketing and management intensive guidance and counseling, increasing the financial and non-financial and public awareness campaign.

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